

ON THE SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ART OF TRANSLATION

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Abstract: The article discusses the unique aspects of the art of translation, the problems of the translation process, and ways to overcome them.

Key words: translation process, invariant, adequate level, form and content, linguistic units, ecbivalent, phrase, stylistic function, tendency, re-creation.

It is known that today knowledge of foreign languages has become the demand of the times, and important attention is being paid not only to knowledge of these subjects, but also to deep learning. Work on translation is of special importance in mastering foreign language speaking skills and competences.

We know that in the process of translation, the text in one language cannot be replaced by the desired text in another language. The translation process is not voluntary, but based on certain rules. If these rules are not followed, it is inappropriate to talk about translation.

A certain invariance must be preserved when converting the text in the original language to the text in the translated language; the level of preservation of this invariant determines the level of alternative or adequacy of the translated text compared to the original text. What remains invariant in the process of translation?

When solving this problem, the following should be taken into account. Each sign has two sides: form and content (meaning). Since language is a unique system of signs, language units also have two sides: both form and meaning. In this regard, the following fact is decisive for the translation:

Different languages have linguistic units that differ in form but are the same in meaning.

For example, German "**Schwester**" the word is Uzbek "**sister**" differs from the word in terms of form, but is the same in meaning.

On this basis, we can emphasize the following. German "**Schwester**" when we replace the word "sister" with the Uzbek word "sister", the translation process is carried out, because these words, which differ in terms of form, are equivalent in terms of meaning. In fact, since a sentence serves as a minimum text (speech piece), the translation process necessarily takes place between at least one sentence (usually several sentences). The situation where the meanings of units belonging to different languages do not correspond to each other is usually eliminated in the sentence.

Based on the example mentioned above, we can say that we only translate German "**Schwester**" word to the Uzbek word "sister" or German of "wohnt". instead of replacing it with the Uzbek word "lives", we replace the entire German sentence "Meine Schwester wohnt in diesem Gebäude" with the Uzbek sentence "My sister lives in this house", in this place the word "lives" it is possible to replace it with the phrase "resides". In both cases, the Uzbek

sentence differs from the original German sentence in terms of form, but is completely similar to it in terms of meaning.

Yuqoridagi fikrlardan kelib chiqib tarjimaga aniqroq ta'rif berish mumkin:

Tarjima deb bir tildagi nutq asarini ikkinchi tildagi nutq asariga o'g'irish, o'zgartirish jarayoniga aytiladi; ushbu jarayonda nutq asarining ma'nosi o'zgarmasdan saqlanib qolishi shart.

In assessing the accuracy of the translation, we use the term "adequacy". Adequate (alternative) translation means that the content of the original text is given clearly and correctly in the translated language. An adequate translation cannot be achieved by translating word for word. For example; "Wie geht es dir?" Literally "How are you?" it would be wrong to translate it as. Depending on the meaning of the sentence, we translate it as follows:

- How are you?
- How are you?
- How are you doing?

Which of these options is considered as an alternative depends on the knowledge and skills of the translator.

If the stylistic function and grammatical form of both languages match, then word-for-word translation is possible.

For example:

My husband is a gift. He received a gift.

Let's consider another example. In German, Russian and Uzbek languages, the number of floors does not correspond to each other.

German der erste Stock, die erste Etage refers to the second floor, not the first floor. The first floor is expressed in German by the words das Erdgeschoß, das Parterre, zuebener Erde.

The combination of words in einer Woche from the German language into the Russian language "cherez nedelyu"; translated into Uzbek as "after a week".

It would be incorrect to translate this combination literally as "в неделю / в течение одной недели", "in one week". The purpose of the translation is to familiarize the reader (or listener) who does not know the original language with the text and content of the work.

To translate is to express clearly and completely in another language what has been expressed once with perfect language tools.

Translation is a tool of direct spiritual communication between nations. Because it conveys works embodying cultural wealth, people's centuries-old noble dreams, ideas and visions to a nation that owns a foreign language. Therefore, translation is a reliable factor of literary influence.

Thanks to translation, the leading trends in world literature, advanced ideas, and artistic discoveries will become closer, create harmony, and unite. By concluding the above thoughts, we can conclude the concept of translation. So, translation is the explanation of ideas expressed in one language to people who speak another language, and if we try to combine the above considerations, it turns out that translation is a complex and multifaceted process.

The main feature of translation is the creative process of re-creating it with other language tools, that is, the art of words. Having concluded these thoughts, we can give a general definition of the concept of translation.

Translation is a huge spiritual bridge that brings people closer to each other and connects hearts. Thanks to the painstaking work of translators throughout the centuries, masterpieces of art, treasures of thought created in the East and the West have spread the seeds of intercontinental friendship, peace, goodness and served in the way of cultural development. Nowadays, translation is a high art, a school of skill. It is a huge creative field that shows the richness, charm, and beauty of the native language. Because of this, he is always treated with great responsibility and demand.

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